

Unified Education System In The Spirit Of Military Patriotism For Students In Pre-Contraction Military Education

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the foundations and objectives of the model of military-patriotic training of students at the Faculty of Military Education, as well as the acquisition of collective knowledge, skills and qualifications.*

Keywords — Fatherland, spiritual, spiritual mastery, skill, intelligence, military-scientific, weapons, military equipment.

INTRODUCTION.

Patriotism is a characteristic feature of a citizen of a person and a certain stage of society, not only pedagogues, but also a significant increase in interest in the problems of education among the general public. It became known that the solution of many tasks in the life of the country depends on the level of citizenship formation in the young generation, the need for spiritual and moral improvement, and a sense of respect for the historical and cultural heritage of the Motherland. That is why the human factor takes the leading place in the defense of the Motherland.

In one of his speeches, the president of our republic, Sh. Mirziyoev, emphasized that spiritual and educational education is a very important, sensitive and decisive issue, and he emphasized the new way of bringing up the patriotic qualities of today's youth. system development tasks were put on the agenda. In this process, our head of state summarized the historical traditions and experiences of foreign countries and gave recommendations such as creating patriotic organizations of children and teenagers in our country on a modern scientific basis. It was emphasized that it is a big mistake to allow red tape, superficiality and laziness in the participation of young people in activities related to military life and physical education, therefore, it is necessary to develop new pedagogical technologies of educating students in the spirit of military patriotism and patriotism. The development of a new methodology for education has become the main goal of today's scientific research.[1]

Also, in the field of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, achieving the full implementation of the tasks defined by the Law "On Education" is an important factor in the formation of patriotic qualities and self-sacrifice in young people.

Based on this goal, the development of effective mechanisms for the development of military-patriotic virtues in young people and the promotion of patriotism in the social sphere have been started, and a system of full use of technical and technological means has been established in this regard. For example, various military-sports competitions and auditions are held in order to form a civic position and responsibility among young people. "Independence", "Amir

Temur", "Jalaluddin Manguberdi" orders, "Jasorat", "For Loyal Services", "Courage" medals were established. Special attention is being paid to the formation of military patriotism among young people. The naming of military academic lyceums as "School of Temurbeks" is a clear proof of our opinion. One of the five priorities for improving the system of state and community building in the Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is "Ensuring security, inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance, and a well-thought-out, mutually beneficial and practical foreign policy" the fact that it is defined as military patriotism makes it necessary to research the scientific problems related to turning military patriotism into a real belief.[2]

On the basis of this research work, by developing in the military-patriotic spirit of the students of military education until the draft, they will develop in them a sense of civic duty, personal responsibility, a sense of belonging to the fate of the Motherland, an active life position and firm faith, and professional skills. was aimed and special methodological tasks were defined for the realization of this goal. Through these tasks, concrete measures are taken to develop the military-patriotic character of the students of military education before the draft, to strengthen the sense of responsibility for the destiny of the motherland, and to educate them to be loyal and mature personnel in all respects. events require us to see.

The social consciousness of patriotism cannot be imagined as a set of individual consciousness of individuals and social groups, which does not have any qualities other than this quantitative description. It would be a mistake to believe that patriotism consists of a set of spiritual consciousness of individual people. Patriotism is a spiritual-practical phenomenon and is not limited to the patriotic consciousness of the society created by individuals, but it should be emphasized that it maintains sufficient independence. Each of these forms of patriotic consciousness - social and individual - presupposes the other and cannot exist without it, their interrelationship and mutual absorption means their inseparable commonality. All this is characteristic of the national consciousness.[3]

At the same time, in recent times there have been attempts to compare the single Fatherland with some of its elements. In 1917, opinions spread that the "replacement" of the Motherland took place with the change of the socio-political

system in our country, that it ceased to exist. In the newspaper material dedicated to the 125th anniversary of Bunin's birth, the writer's reference to our country "which disappeared in such a short time..." is given.

In fact, almost 90 years ago, radical changes took place in the concrete-historical content of the Motherland, but its "eternal" elements remained relatively unchanged and still exist. Usually, it is impossible to betray the Motherland without betraying any element of it. Also, it is impossible to generalize the country with one or more of its elements, even with its important elements, such as the political, economic and social environment.

This classification of patriotism is based on the separation of its subject and object, which allows us to see this multifaceted social phenomenon in its entirety and harmonious unity, and thus to confirm the existence of any commonality in a separate and unique way. will give.

Therefore, patriotism is expressed as a set of many types in everyday life. In this regard, their based classification is of great scientific and practical importance. It is necessary to recognize the need to prioritize the national content of patriotism; Love for the native land, care for the preservation and purity of the native language, pride for the achievements of the country in science, culture and technology, etc. are all elements of the national-ethnic aspect of this socio-cultural phenomenon.

In addition to the national-ethnic aspect, there is also a universal democratic content (human rights and freedoms, the rule of law, etc.) and all this together defines patriotism as an important integrating factor that unites society. It can be emphasized that patriotism is focused on people who represent the subject and object.[4]

This is the main difference between real patriotism and abstract patriotism, which implies an essentially aimless desire for the good of the country. Patriotism has no meaning without service to the country and people, which form the basis of life. The formula of patriotism "land for land" has no meaning without the people living in these lands. Patriotism that is not directed to human needs is a concept.

Accordingly, all types of patriotism (political, economic, social spheres, etc.) are aimed at improving the living conditions of the population, that is, at its mass subjects and objects of patriotic relations. Unreasonable changes in one or another area of the Motherland, which lead to deterioration of people's quality of life, are considered against patriotism. Therefore, when describing the types of patriotism, it is necessary to pay attention to its implementation from the point of view of people's interests and needs. There are many examples of "unnatural" love for our country, which is expressed by complete indifference, even hatred towards the people.

Local patriotism includes localism, regionalism, collective patriotism, etc. Contrasting local, own and national interests and needs serve as sources of their expression. In our country, such processes took place especially strongly in the last decade

of the 20th century. Without revealing the political, social and other reasons for this incident, we emphasize that the indicated negative circumstances have not been completely eliminated. Of course, local patriotism has nothing in common with localism as a distorted form of nationalism. It is more difficult to distinguish true patriotism, which harmoniously includes love for a small Motherland, from false patriotism, which is limited to such love.[5]

Philosophical basis is breaking the dialectic of part and whole. Historical experience testifies that prosperous regions can be found only in a prosperous country. It is impossible to talk about the small Motherland in isolation from the Big Motherland. This approach to the understanding of patriotism is especially unacceptable for military personnel who serve to protect the common Motherland.

It is necessary to emphasize the territorial aspect of state and local patriotism. Honoring the place of ancestors is one of the ancient historical phenomena of patriotism. It is in this context that it is possible to emphasize that the foundations of patriotism were created before the appearance of the objects of patriotism - dependent homelands. Many researchers have pointed out that in ancient peoples, a clearer understanding of the Motherland was connected with family activities. Answering the question of how a person should treat his land, N. Berdyaev wrote as follows: "The image of mother earth is not only the image of a mother, it is also the image of a bride and wife... and the image of a child. A person without love for his land will be powerless in any business, land occupation".[2]

The sense of homeland begins with the childhood memory of each person's home, yard, city or village. That is, love for the motherland arises in a true patriot in childhood and accompanies him throughout his life. The region with which the history of the people is connected and the corner of the motherland where each of us grew up are directly interconnected and are considered one of the deep sources of patriotism. A properly developed sense of the land of our ancestors should help us understand the whole territory of the country in general. In fact, each of its subjects has its own territory, but all of them form a single territory of the country. It is important to understand the importance of issues such as the integrity of the homeland, its inseparability, historical and legal rights to the territory.[5]

Summary. Formation of preparation for homeland defense. we emphasize that it refers to the great work to be done with the young generation, especially in modern conditions. This is confirmed by the existence of objectively valid social-political, spiritual, military-technical factors.

The problem of military-patriotic training of reserve students in higher professional education at civilian HEIs should be considered in the context of studying the concept of "patriotism", which is defined in scientific literature as principle, feeling, commitment, readiness (psychological), idea, is seen as awareness. Such a variety of approaches to defining the essence of the concept is primarily related to the complexity and versatility of this social phenomenon.

Military-patriotic education, on the other hand, is aimed at forming a deep sense of patriotism in a person, the idea of serving the Motherland and its armed defense, respect for military history, striving for military service, preserving and increasing military traditions. is a structural component of the system of patriotic education. In other words, this is a psychological-pedagogical process that ensures the formation of special qualities of a patriotic military person.

Currently, this direction is especially relevant due to the decline in the prestige of military professions, the reluctance of many young people to serve in the army, and the revision of history.

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